

How Connectivity is Transforming the Automotive Ecosystem

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This paper brings together both a technical and a business approach about the introduction of wireless communications in vehicles and how this is affecting the automotive sector. It also provides complementary insights on how business opportunities can affect the selection of different available wireless technologies. Different perspectives on how the automotive sector is being transformed are also described.

KEYWORDS

V2X, Connected Vehicles, Digital Transformation, Business Ecosystem, 5G, 802.11p

1 | INTRODUCTION

The automotive ecosystem is going through a profound transformation, partly, because of the introduction of Internet of Things (IoT) and new emerging technologies [7]. Vehicles have become one of the *things* that will be soon interconnected and Internet-connected. In fact, they can collect, use, and send information concerning speed, weather, driving conditions, or location, to make driving safer, more efficient, and more comfortable. Accordingly, vehicles are evolving into mobile computing centers which can exchange information through wireless communications. This way, vehicles can become more aware of their environment and increase their level of automation. Vehicle manufacturers, ICT companies, and other stakeholders are taking advantage of this opportunity and looking into ways of collaboration to provide innovative services. The whole value chain of the automotive sector is evolving to integrate emerging actors. In this new ecosystem, different industries need to cooperate and compete simultaneously to address new business opportunities. There are various decisions to make for each of the key players in this market, including which business strategies should be followed, or which technologies will be adopted.

A key enabler of this evolving context is *connectivity*. Concerning the automotive sector, connectivity is about the

communication between vehicles and other vehicles (V2V), infrastructure (V2I), pedestrians (V2P), and the network (V2N); all these together are commonly referred to as Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications. Today, there are two major technologies competing for this market in Europe: one is based on the IEEE 802.11p Standard; the other one is based on standardized cellular networks promoted by the 3GPP, i.e., LTE, 5G and beyond. While factors such as the radio performance can determine the adoption of these technologies, the businesses that can be built on top of these technologies will also become key determining factors for their success.

In this paper, we aim at providing complementary insights on how business opportunities can affect the adoption of different wireless technologies, and the other way around. We compare the two main available V2X technologies and explore the businesses that can be built on top of them. Particular focus is put on 5G technologies. To do so, we also discuss the added value that V2X communications can bring to both the automotive sector and the telecom industry. To carry out this qualitative research study, data collection activities have been necessary. Extensive literature review has been carried out including: contributions to standards, whitepapers from automotive alliances, techno-economic research publications, websites of official car makers, and market research studies. These references are mostly from 2015 onwards. In addition, we have carried out semi-structured interviews with experts inside Ericsson, representatives from Mobile Network Operators (MNO) and automotive companies, as well as with Internet of Things (IoT) experts.

2 | V2X COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

V2X communications enable new possibilities by involving a vehicle as a source or destination of the exchange of information. The applications enabled by V2X can be classified into three groups: 1) road safety, 2) traffic efficiency, and 3) infotainment [4]. Today, there are two main V2X technologies which are being considered [5].

1. Technologies based on the IEEE 802.11p Standard; ETSI ITS-G5 promoted in Europe, and Dedicated Short Range Communications (DSRC) promoted in the US.
2. Standardized cellular-based technologies; based on 3GPP LTE/5G specifications.

The IEEE 802.11p has been designed for V2X communications, with focus on V2V safety applications. It operates in the 5.9 GHz frequency band, reserved for ITS services in Europe and the US. This technology is already available and has been validated in multiple field trials [6]. However, it has shortcomings in V2X applications: for example, the technology can reach 5 ms latency with high reliability, but only in optimal situations. Experiments have shown that the performance is extremely sensitive to large vehicle densities, high traffic load, and high vehicle speed [8, 9, 12]. Under these conditions, the performance degrades rapidly and the required latency is no longer achieved. Furthermore, deploying the infrastructure required for V2I depends on government authorities and business cases have not been clearly defined yet. Moreover, this technology cannot support highly demanding services such as infotainment, remote diagnostics, and autonomous vehicles where delay-critical and highly-reliable services are involved.

In its turn, the 3GPP is promoting a standard for V2X communications re-using cellular infrastructure; generally referred to as LTE-V. This technology is being designed to operate both at the 5,9 Ghz band and also in cellular spectrum allocated for general purposes. LTE-V has two transmission modes: 1) infrastructure-based (routing data traffic through the base stations), and 2) direct communication between vehicles using device-to-device (D2D) communications. The use of D2D can be either network-assisted or completely ad-hoc [12]. D2D communications can reduce end-to-end latency, increase network capacity, and reduce energy consumption [10]. LTE-V technology cannot meet yet the performance requirements needed to cover all possible V2X communications use cases. In fact, the reliability and availability decrease in high speed or high density environments [11] and the Quality of Service (QoS) cannot be guaranteed in all cases. For this reason, efforts to further evolve LTE-V technology continue¹.

¹The collaborative European project 5GCAR, integrated by key stakeholders of the automotive industry, constitutes a representative example of the European

TABLE 1 Comparison between 802.11p-based and LTE-V technologies. Theoretical Values are shown.

Variables	ITS-G5	LTE (Rel.14)	5G
Currently Available	Yes	Yes	No
Multiple Field Trials (+10 years)	Yes	No	No
Support for Multimedia & Cloud based Services	No	Yes	Yes
Applications	V2V, V2I	V2V, V2I, V2N	V2V, V2I, V2N
V2V Latency	5 ms	20 ms	<5 ms
Range up to (aprox.):	300 m	500 m	Few km
Data rate:	3 to 27 Mbps	Up to 150 Mbps	Up to 10 Gbps
Autonomous SAE level support:	0, 1 & 2	0, 1 & 2	Up to 4

Data Sources: [4, 1, 6, 8]

5G technology promises to deliver extreme low levels of latency (below 5ms) and very high reliability and service availability. 5G technologies feature network slicing enabled by Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). These technologies will make it possible to build the communications network in the form of programmable platforms which deliver different levels of QoS and functionality depending on the application requirements, as-a-service basis. Table 1 shows a comparison between these technologies, indicating that 5G promises to outperform the other two technologies.

3 | THE AUTOMOTIVE TRANSFORMATION ENABLED BY CONNECTIVITY

The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) has defined the 6 levels of autonomy shown in Figure 1: from 0, where the driver has total control of the vehicle, to 5, where the vehicle is fully autonomous [14]. These levels can be split into 2 categories depending on who monitors the driving environment: the human category from level 0 to 2, and the system category from level 3 to 5. Commercially available technologies to date can only cover up to level 2 [6]. The main reason is that once the automated system becomes responsible for monitoring the driving environment and making decisions, the reliability and availability of the required services must be completely guaranteed with no room for failures whenever human lives are involved. Therefore, the transformation of the automotive sector will be tightly coupled to the evolution of the enabling technologies.

For example, technologies based on the IEEE 802.11p Standard will bring, at least, chip manufacturers and transport authorities into the automotive ecosystem. The major transformation that this will cause is due to the need to deploy and maintain the required infrastructure for connectivity. Tight collaboration with these players will be needed to define common communication standards.

In the US, the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration proposed to enforce V2V communications using the IEEE 802.11p technology for all new vehicles. This mandate could have had a profound impact into the market. However, wireless industry companies, automakers (e.g. Mercedes and BMW), and chip suppliers (e.g. Qualcomm) publicly sent comments and asked to also consider cellular-based technologies, thus making the mandate technologically neutral². Therefore, it is not clear which technology will be the dominating one, or if the two technologies will coexist in harmony.

It is important to emphasize that there are two main types of services in the automotive industry: commercial and ITS services. The first type includes, for example, navigation, media streaming on cars, and WiFi hotspots, which cannot

effort to contribute to this development towards 5G technologies. For more information about the project, visit the website: <https://5gcar.eu/>

²<https://www.regulations.gov/docket?D=NHTSA-2016-0090>

FIGURE 1 Different levels of Autonomy according to the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) and technology supporting these levels.

be covered by the IEEE 802.11p technology. These are the services with more and better defined business models potential today. In their turn, ITS services, focused on safety and traffic efficiency, are still uncertain from the business model perspective. Based on these classification of services, Cadillac was the first OEM to introduce V2V on its vehicles. It uses cellular LTE from AT&T for its infotainment *OnStar* platform, but uses an IEEE 802.11p modem for safety-related V2V communications which could be, eventually, replaced by the cellular-based technology. This is a particular case where the two technologies complement each other.

In Europe, the European Commission has approved a regulation which requires all new cars to be equipped with emergency call (eCall) technology from April 2018 [13]. Consequently, new cars will be equipped with a cellular modem. Since this emergency service will not enable OEM companies to differentiate from each other, it is expected that they will explore the creation of new connectivity services. For example, OEMs may decide to integrate a sophisticated LTE modem which can take full advantage of V2X communications, beyond emergency services (eCall), and create new services which can turn into new forms of revenues either directly or indirectly. The differentiation among competing car vendors may be played in this field. In their turn, MNOs may look for this differentiation by expanding their networks to offer network-assisted services with the help of road authorities, as it is already being done in smart city projects.

The EU-funded research action 5GCAR, in addition to technology development, will also focus on the business perspective of innovative V2X use cases which include cooperative perception (see-through), cooperative maneuver (lane merge), cooperative safety (vulnerable road user protection), autonomous navigation, and remote driving.

4 | THE NEW AUTOMOTIVE BUSINESS ECOSYSTEM

It is expected that the addressable share by new entrants in the auto industry will grow to more than 45% by 2030 [3]. In order to create a stable ecosystem, actors need to define their position, links with each other, and the activities that need to be undertaken to enable new capabilities [2]. Cooperation is needed: telecom actors need to provide their infrastructure and licensed spectrum, and the automotive suppliers need to create the chips and sensors compatible with the technology. The typical value chain is transforming into an ecosystem where the relationships between the actors are still uncertain. Actors thus need to share knowledge and resources. At the same time, competition arises in other activities, such as the provision of the necessary services. Actors providing key services for the automotive sector can be split into: 1) Those providing service enabling platforms, which manage the data and allow services to be built on top of the data, and 2) Those enabling connectivity, which use and manage connectivity over cellular networks. This second group is becoming increasingly relevant as automakers start using GSMA Embedded SIM cards (eSIM).

FIGURE 2 Different perspectives on how connectivity and new services can change the automotive value chain.

These eSIM cards are fixed (non-removable), remotely provisioned, and store one or more MNO profiles. One of the key functionalities is that they can switch between operators in case of no coverage; this can be crucial for high autonomous levels. This transition and the different possible ecosystems that can be created are illustrated in figure 2. Four different possibilities are shown, depending on who provides the platform (highlighted circle). Different actors have their own solution ready for OEM. Examples of these solutions are described in Table 2.

MNOs have a challenge ahead: they will need to support V2X cellular communications in the near future. During an interview, an MNO smart city expert stated that V2X might not be interesting for operators because the possibilities for usage-based billing are limited; this becomes particularly true if communications take place in the unlicensed 5.9GHz band. In addition, today V2X messages mostly carry information which can be obtained from other sources, such as location via a GPS modem. Other opinions argue that this scenario can be advantageous to MNOs due to the fact that while communication happens through unlicensed spectrum, they still have control over the exchanged data.

TABLE 2 Current ecosystem transformation possibilities based on the platform enablers, real solutions, and advantages of adopting them for OEMs.

	New activity	Example	Main advantage for OEM
OEM	Service/connectivity platform	Tesla uses an in-house cloud platform to build own services on top of it and partners directly with MNOs.	No sharing revenue streams. Higher data control.
AS	Service platform providers	Bosch IoT Cloud Suite, partnered with TomTom, has ready-to-use cloud services.	Trust, have been partnered with OEM before.
TEV	Service or/and connectivity platform providers	Ericsson has solutions for enabling connectivity and services such as the Connected Vehicles Cloud and a specific Vehicle Marketplace for building applications on top.	Partners with many MNOs, good position for connectivity platform providers if multiple MNOs (eSIM).
MNO	Service or/and connectivity platform and device.	Cadillac platform OnStar work through AT&T connectivity. Other MNOs are also providing service platforms such as Telia Sense, partnering directly with EasyPark.	Connectivity providers already partners for infotainment applications.
New-Comers	Service or/and connectivity platform providers	Cubic Telecom partners with MNOs and handles Audi’s eSIM connectivity. Otonomo car data exchange platform for new applications.	Flexible to adapt and tailored to the market.

5 | CONCLUSION

Connecting things does not create value by itself. It is what you do with the connectivity what will ultimately create value. In order to create value, the focus shall be set on the data that is coming to and from vehicles, and can be exchanged through wireless connectivity. For this particular reason, adding connectivity to the automotive ecosystem is causing a profound transformation in the sector. Business leaders across different industries involved in the automotive ecosystem are looking into ways of handling the implications of this transformation.

Actors from the telecom and automotive sector, as well as digital "new-comers", need each other to make this transformation possible. At the same time, they are turning into competitors aiming at making profit from the new services that will be available. This paper has described different perspectives on how the ecosystem can be built; the aim is to show the potential of cellular-based solutions to create innovative V2X-enabled services which provide added value. The business perspective presented in this paper has shown that one of the key challenges for the creation of V2X services related to road safety and traffic efficiency is the lack of clear and well-defined business models. A possible outcome of this analysis is that, in a first stage, the telecom sector may leverage on cellular-based solutions to create services which do not involve low latency or high reliability communications, which will be left for a future stage once technology is mature enough. This approach could lead to the investment into new mobility services, enabled by either autonomous or semi-autonomous vehicles, which may lead to the provision of new services, and eventually, the creation of new revenue streams.

REFERENCES

- [1] 5G Americas. White Paper: V2X Cellular Solutions 2016;.
- [2] Adner R. Ecosystem as Structure : An Actionable Construct for Strategy 2017;43(1):39–58.
- [3] Baker EH, Crusius D, Fischer M, Gerling W, Gnanaserakan K, Kerstan H, et al. Connected Car Report 2016: Opportunities, Risk, and Turmoil on the Road to Autonomous Vehicles. Strategy& 2016;p. 1–64.
- [4] Chen S, Hu J, Shi Y, Zhao L. LTE-V: A TD-LTE-Based V2X Solution for Future Vehicular Network. IEEE Internet of Things Journal 2016;3(6):997–1005.
- [5] European Commission. Study on the Deployment of C-ITS in Europe : Final Report 2016;p. 218.
- [6] Festag A. Standards for vehicular communication—from IEEE 802.11p to 5G. e & i Elektrotechnik und Informationstechnik 2015;132.
- [7] Ghanbari A, Laya A, Alonso-Zarate J, Markendahl J. Business Development in the Internet of Things: A Matter of Vertical Cooperation. IEEE Communications Magazine 2017;55(2):135–141.
- [8] Hameed Mir Z, Filali F. LTE and IEEE 802.11p for vehicular networking: a performance evaluation. EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking 2014;2014(1).
- [9] Jutila M, Scholliers J, Valta M, Kujanpää K. ITS-G5 performance improvement and evaluation for vulnerable road user safety services. IET Intelligent Transport Systems 2017;11(3):126–133.
- [10] Laya A, Alonso L, Alonso-Zarate J. Efficient contention resolution in highly dense LTE networks for machine type communications. 2015 IEEE Global Communications Conference, GLOBECOM 2015 2015;p. 1–7.
- [11] Luoto P, Bennis M, Pirinen P, Samarakoon S, Horneman K, Latva-aho M, et al. System Level Performance Evaluation of LTE-V2X Network 2016;p. 2–6.
- [12] Min W, Winbjörk M, Zhang Z, Blasco R, Do H, Sorrentino S, et al. Comparison of LTE and DSRC-Based Connectivity for Intelligent Transportation Systems 2017;.
- [13] Official Journal of the European Union. Regulation (EU) 2015/758 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2015 concerning type-approval requirements for the deployment of the eCall in-vehicle system based on the 112 service and amending Directive 2007/46/EC;.
- [14] SAE INTERNATIONAL. Automated Driving Levels of Driving Automation are defined in new SAE international standard J3016. Sae International 2014;https://www.sae.org/misc/pdfs/automated{_}driving.pdf.